

DESIGNING FOLDABLE COMPOSITE STRUCTURES ON THE MICROMETRE SCALE

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Keywords: Thin-Ply Composites, Foldable Structures, Ultra-thin Structures, Deployable Structures

ABSTRACT

High performance applications requiring high specific strength and stiffness are taking advantage of thin-ply composite materials. Additionally, these materials can enable novel functionalities beyond the classical application in lightweight structures. We show that thin fiber reinforced composite structures can be utilized to create stiff self-expandable structures that can be packaged into tight volumes and expand to more than twice their packaged size. We extend the capabilities of foldable and expandable structures to lower scales, demonstrating that continuous cylindrical composite shells can be designed and manufactured to have the potential to act as cardiovascular implants. The design of expandable cylindrical structures made from fiber reinforced composites, however, faces a number of challenges including large strain flexural behaviour, material and manufacturing imperfections in the micrometre regime as well as structural anisotropy. To find the stiffest layup that can be packaged into a given catheter size, we combine large deformation experimental procedures, microscopic structural analysis and non-linear finite element analysis and investigate the complex relation between packaging scheme, structural anisotropy and the consideration of unavoidable manufacturing induced imperfections. Results can lead to a predictable design of a continuous composite shell at the scale of an aortic stent, that can adapt its diameter by more than 2.5 times and is stiff enough to expand inside a confined environment like a human artery.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern Tow-Spreading techniques and impregnation processes for prepreg materials allow the manufacturing of high quality composite plies with areal weights below 20g/m^2 [1]. Recent studies showed that the use of such thin-ply composites instead of thicker plies drastically increases stiffness and strength of a structure [1,2]. While the increasing complexity and manufacturing time is preventing an efficient use in standard engineering, such materials are predestined for structures that require maximum specific strength and stiffness. Successful utilization of thin-ply composites [3–5] can be found in space structures, where satellites have to be efficiently packaged in the constrained volume of a launcher vehicle. Low ply counts of the material enable elastic folding of the thin structures that can afterwards be deployed using the stored elastic energy of the composite.

Foldable composite structures face contradicting requirements: Providing structural support and stiffness while being deformable enough to be efficiently packaged. Similar requirements can be found in cardiovascular stents, which also require tight packaging for delivery and structural rigidity after expansion [6–8], however to date did not utilize foldable composites. Modern stents for the delivery of artificial heart valves for example [6] are cylindrical structures that expand from diameters of 12mm to diameters of 29mm and fixate prosthetic valves in the human aorta. Applying a similar concept for expandable stents as for modern space structures offers distinct advantages over commonly metal mesh-like structures such as larger fixation forces, continuous loading of the aorta as well as self-expansion.

However, the utilization of composites for expandable stent structures in the millimetre scale faces a number of design challenges: Composites show no plasticity or super elasticity as common metal stents. Instead, they have to rely on purely elastic folding and strain energy deployment. This requires the structure to be as stiff as possible to expand and stretch a confined environment. Simultaneously

the structure has to be packaged into a constrained space of a few millimetres. As a consequence, a laminate design has to be found that allows to fold the stiffest 29mm structure into a given diameter of 12mm. Therefore, the laminate has to withstand bending radii of only a few millimetres which results in structure thickness in the micrometre scale. At such low scale, this requires the consideration of effects, that are usually neglected in classic composite design. Manufacturing and material imperfections strongly influence the structure's behaviour as they span a significant part of the structure thickness and cannot be assumed to cancel out over the different plies [9–11]. In combination with the complex material behaviour based on size effects [12–14], the performance as well as the efficient packaging of those structures is difficult to predict and requires novel design methodologies.

This paper will show reliable ways to design foldable ultra-thin composite structures that face the contradicting challenge of minimizing packaging diameters while maximizing a structure stiffness. While this challenge is frequently found in space structure design, this paper extends it to smaller scales by demonstrating a potential novel application as expandable implants. This requires the experimental verification of withstandable bending radii of layups of 100 μ m thickness, the analysis of the impact of material and manufacturing imperfections on the structure design as well as a reliable prediction of acting loads and resulting shapes during packaging. To validate the design, a demonstrator structure will be manufactured, folded and expanded in a confined environment.

2 CONCEPT OF A FOLDABLE AND SELF EXPANDABLE COMPOSITE CYLINDER

Efficient radial packaging of an ultra-thin composite cylinder follows a two-step folding procedure and is illustrated in Figure 1. The folding pattern is inspired by the higher order buckling modes of a free ring under hydrostatic pressure [15,16]. These buckling modes ensure a reduction in effective diameter of the structure (Folding Stage 1) and allow radial expansion from its elastically buckled state, once the buckling loads are released (Figure 1, second row).

The folded structures are created through equally distributed pinching loads forming the lobed structures. Following the buckled state, the packaging efficiency $\eta = (R_0 - R_C)/R_0$, which is defined as the diameter change achieved through packaging with respect to the initial diameter, can be drastically increased by a second folding step. In this step, the formed lobes are chirally twisted around eccentric axes and afterwards enclosed by a cylindrical constraint, which prevents the elastic structure from opening. The structure is self-equilibrating and deploys autonomously when pushed out of its cylindrical constraint.

Figure 1: Schematic of the folding and expansion process of radially expandable composite shells

By maximizing the arc length of the folded structure inside a constraint of radius R_C we can obtain the optimum packaging efficiency of a structure consisting of three packaging radii: The internal radius R_1 , the twisting radius R_2 and the lobe tip radius R_3 (Top row in Figure 1). Following scale and mechanical requirements of state-of-the-art stents for delivery of artificial heart valves [6], the three radii that fit the largest continuous structure folded inside a constraint with radius of 6mm can be seen

in Table 1. Since this paper focusses on the composite design of such a folded structure, the derivation of the optimum combination of radii is not shown for simplicity.

R_0 <i>Initial Cylinder Radius</i>	R_1 <i>Internal Folding Radius</i>	R_2 <i>Twisting Radius</i>	R_3 <i>Lobe Tip Radius</i>	R_C <i>Packaged Radius</i>
14.5 mm	5.8 mm	1.6 mm	1.9 mm	6 mm

Table 1: Geometrically optimal combination of packaging radii for a stent-scale composite structure (For definition of radii see Figure 1).

Such a folded structure deploys effortlessly in a free environment, however this would not necessary be the case in a confined environment like for example a human artery (yellow vessel in Figure 1). Successful deployment in a confined environment can only be achieved when the reaction forces between the confinement and structure during deployment are lower than its critical buckling pressure. Hence, successful deployment is directly dependent on the bending stiffness of the deploying structure. In case of a successful deployment, the structure will be able to remain circular and stretch the confining vessel, creating a radial fixation force. In case of an unsuccessful deployment, the structure bifurcates into a buckled elastically confined ring [17]. Hence to avoid failure, the design process must yield a structure with the highest critical buckling pressure, which still being able to withstand the folding radii. This is a contradiction also commonly associated with deployable space structure design, where structures have to be packaged as tightly as possible to save stowage volume while being stiff enough to withstand maneuvers in space [5,18].

3 LARGE DEFORMATION MATERIAL TESTING OF ULTRA-THIN COMPOSITE SPECIMENS

The critical bending radius and the structural stiffness can be largely tuned by utilizing the anisotropy in composite materials, however no data currently exists that characterizes the bending behavior at such low radii for different fiber angle specimens. To investigate the bending behavior at the micrometer scale, we conducted large deformation bending tests on thin-ply carbon fiber epoxy material [19,20]. The ultra-thin composite specimen consisted of a 20 gsm unidirectional prepreg (Toray T700S fibers embedded in a ThinPreg™ 402 epoxy matrix). Specimen were manufactured on a carbon fiber reinforced mold to eliminate post-cure deformation in the sensitive specimens due to CTE-mismatches between the mold and part [9–11] as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Prepreg sheets laid up on a CFRP mold (left) and different fiber orientation angle specimens with specified in-plane dimensions (right).

The composite layup was then covered by a perforated release foil, a breather and a vacuum foil and cured in an autoclave at a temperature of 120° for 4 hours and at a pressure of 5 bar. Symmetric and balanced specimens with 5 samples per fiber orientation of 0°, ±15°, ±30°, ±45° and ±60° (0° in bending direction) were manufactured and investigated with regard to their thickness under an optical

microscope. The 4-ply specimens average thicknesses of 82 μm . Figure 3 shows the micrograph of a 0° specimen. It is worth to note that slightly lower thicknesses are observed for 0° specimens (80 μm) due to more efficient fiber packing in the absence of fiber crossings.

Figure 3: Micrograph at 20X magnification of a 0° UD specimen. Picture evidences of a flat surface on the mold side and a slightly higher roughness on the surface in contact with the flexible vacuum bag.

To test the bending behavior of the specimens, two flat platen compression fixtures were manufactured and fixed to a Zwick Roell testing machine with a load cell of 5kN (Figure 4). The test was recorded with a Nikon D5300 with N-series camera lens NIKKOR (105mm 1:2.8G) with the goal of post-processing the last images of the movie with MATLAB and obtain measurements of maximum curvature (κ) and distance between the coupon mid-point and the point of separation from the plate.

Figure 4: Bending platen test setup with a camera positioned in front of the Zwick machine (left) and detailed view of the compression fixtures with duct tape used to fix the specimen (right). The ruler is needed to provide scale for optical measurements.

Using a circle detection function (Circular Hough Transformation) we were able to extract the minimum radius achieved by each specimen at the image closest to material failure. Using knowledge of the specimen thickness, we are able to estimate the maximum linear bending strain from the relation (1), where κ is the curvature at failure and t_{shell} the overall specimen thickness.

$$\varepsilon_{b,max} = \kappa \cdot t_{shell} / 2 \quad (1)$$

The results can be seen in Figure 6, which shows that ultimate failure of the specimen follows an exponential trend as a function of fiber angle.

Figure 6: Minimum achievable bending radius as a function of fiber angle in 4-Ply balanced and symmetric layups.

As expected, ultimate failure is delayed with increasing fiber angle allowing for lower bending radii. However, the bending stiffness also drops significantly with increasing fiber angle. It can be observed that below a 30° fiber angle it is not recommended to use angled plies, since the knockdown in stiffness is large without a noticeable improvement in critical bending radius.

4 LAYUP DESIGN AND FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATIONS

The material testing provided fundamental knowledge about ultimately withstandable curvatures in angle ply layups. Based on the designed packaging scheme and the critical bending strain obtained from the material tests, the stiffest layups, which are still able to withstand the bending radii required by the packaging scheme, are chosen. Therefore, we introduce a ratio,

$$\rho_{Layup} = D_{11} \cdot \kappa_{max} = D_{11} \cdot t_{shell} / 2\varepsilon_{b,max}, \quad (2)$$

which combines the plate bending stiffness from classical lamination theory (ABD-Matrix $-D_{11}$) with the maximum achievable strain obtained from the material tests ($\varepsilon_{b,max}$). Layups with a large value of ρ are desirable, since they can be packaged tightly without failure and still provide structural support. With a desired value of κ_{max} dictated by the packaging scheme (Table 1), only a few layups can be assembled which can withstand the smallest required packaging radius. As the structure should be as stiff as possible to also deploy in constrained environments, possible ply counts can only be varied between four and six plies. Three layup alternatives are displayed in Table 2.

<i>Layup Number #</i>	<i>Layup-Pattern</i>	<i>Overall Thickness t_{shell}</i>	<i>Plate bending stiffness D_{11}</i>	<i>Minimum Bending Radius R_{min}</i>	ρ_{Layup}	ABD-Properties
1	[0]₄	81.16 μm	5.97 Nmm	1.38 mm	4.33	Unidirectional
2	[60]-60 0]_s	127.98 μm	3.1 Nmm	1.22 mm	2.54	Symmetric and balanced
3	[-30 0 0]+30]	83.14 μm	3.83 Nmm	1.25 mm	3.06	Skew-Symmetric

Table 2: Possible layups that can withstand the desired packaging scheme. The 0° fiber angle for the cylindrical shell is defined in circumferential direction (same as in the material testing).

Apart from the evident tradeoff between layup thickness and fiber angle, the three different layup types show different deformation properties. Taking large deformations of the shell into account, non-negligible bend-twist coupling terms D_{16} and D_{26} which are present in layup 2 will effect the folding performance of the structure. Obviously, one can release the symmetry constraint and create so called “skew-symmetric layups” like layup 3. These layups trade bend-twist coupling terms with a non-zero B-Matrix. The resulting couplings are however less critical to the pure bending case and allow for more reliable folding. Although layup 1 shows the best overall performance, the unidirectional layup will be prone to unforeseen off-axis loading due to the limited transverse strength of the composite. All three layups will furthermore be considered in the design process.

The combination of bending radii leading to the predicted packaged radius (Table 1) is purely geometrical and does not yet consider possible deformations due to self-contact of the structure inside the constraint. To predict the ultimate packaged state and therefore the strain state in the material, we developed a non-linear finite element model in ABAQUS/Standard which consists out of S4R shell elements. The material is modelled with linear elastic orthotropic properties of $E_{11} = 139$ GPa, $E_{22} = 8,72$ GPa, $G_{12} = 3.39$ GPa and $\nu_{12} = 0.23$ which result from a fiber volume content of 58%.

The structure is pinched with three rigid pinching bodies, with the estimated radii from the geometrical prediction (Table 1), travelling on equally distributed radial paths till they come in contact with each other and the first folding stage is completed. In a second folding step, rigid body cylinders located inside the lobe tips with radius R_3 travel on involute paths around the pinching bodies, until a rigid cylinder can enclose the folded structure and the internal constraints (Folding jig) can be removed. The process can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The folding process of the structure in non-linear finite element simulation

With that, we can obtain the strain developing in the material at different stages of the folding process. Figure 6 shows the strain in the innermost ply for different folding steps and for the three considered layups once the rigid bodies are removed.

Figure 6: Strain during different folding stages (left) and comparison of different layups (right) after jig removal including the critical bending strain from material testing (dotted line).

It becomes evident that once the rigid bodies required to force the composite shell into its folded state are removed, the structure self-equilibrates and creates an additional internal loading on the outer lobes. Hence, the most critical strain state is created at the very last stage of the folding process. The maximum strain also does not only occur in radius R_2 (Position: $\theta \approx 95^\circ$), as predicted by the geometric model. In addition, the lobe tip R_3 (Position: $\theta \approx 60^\circ$) is also heavily loaded as a consequence of the internal strain energy pressing the structure against its cylindrical constraint. Furthermore, the stresses at R_2 are intensified due to the self-equilibration of the structure. Combining simulation and material testing (Figure 6, right), it can be seen, that Layup 2 and 3 show slight safety margins ($\sim 5\%$) (including standard deviation), however Layup 1 is likely to fail due to the intensified strains from the jig removal.

5 MANUFACTURING PROCESS

The manufacturing process of the ultra-thin expandable rings is based on the wrapping of a thin-ply staggered layup around a cylindrical mandrel as can be seen in Figure 7. The staggering ensures a controllable ply distribution over the circumference of the cylinder. However, the wrapping process also introduces fundamental imperfections that have to be taken into account during the design process. Even with perfectly cut plies and highest wrapping accuracy, one cannot fully avoid gaps or overlaps in the wrapped plies. To get a predictable structure, a constant overlap length δ_{OL} is introduced (Figure 7). The overlap length ensures sufficient continuity between a single wrapped ply to transfer loads among itself. Hence, the length of a staggered patch of thin ply material has the length $2\pi R_0 + \delta_{OL}$. The position of the overlaps within the structure can be influenced with the staggering length L_S . Once staggered, the layup is wrapped around the mandrel with a diameter of 29mm, which is covered with a PTFE shrink hose (to facilitate demolding of the thin structures). After wrapping, the structure is covered with perforated release foil and compacted with a rubber shrink hose and a heat gun, to prevent an imprint of the following breather layer on the surface. The structure is vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave under 120 degrees and 5 bar pressure. After demolding, the structure is cut to cylinders of 15mm length and the edges sanded to remove edge cracks resulting from cutting.

Figure 7: Manufacturing Process of ultra-thin deployable rings (left) and overlap strategy (right)

The manufactured cylinder was casted into clear casting epoxy and micrographed along its circumference. Figure 8 shows the microscopic measurement of a cylinder with Layup 2 (Table 2) and a constant staggering length $L_S=0.5\pi R_0$, which results in equally distributed overlaps along the circumference. The thickness measurements are divided in three layers, the inner layer consisting of the first $\pm 60^\circ$ plies that are directly in contact with the mold, the mid layer which consists of the two 0-degree plies and the outer layer, again consisting out of $\pm 60^\circ$ plies which are forming the outer surface of the part. The sum of the layers results in the total thickness, which can be seen in the top black plot. The equally distributed overlaps can be identified as distinct peaks in the total- as well as the single layer thickness. The statistical analysis of over 700 measurements along the circumference is summarized in Table 3.

Figure 8: Thickness Profile along the circumference of the manufactured cylinder (left) and micrographs of the manufactured shell (right).

In general, the layers in contact with the smooth mold surface (inner layer) as well as the unidirectional 0-degree layer are more uniform than the outer layer. The outer plies have more pronounced thickness variations, since the imperfections of the inner plies print through the layup towards the surface. The average structural thickness of $122.4\mu\text{m}$ correlates well with the expected one from fiber volume content and manufacturer's data sheet ($120\mu\text{m}$). Although the standard

deviation for the single layers lies within a single fiber diameter, it causes thickness variations of up to 10%, which has significant influence on the given strain state. Assuming that the fiber thickness follows a Gaussian distribution, 5% of all the measurements are expected to be 17% thicker than the average structure thickness. With the bending strain being highly dependent on the structure thickness, this results in strain peaks of additional 8.5%. In the region of a ply overlap this results in a maximum measured thickness of 135% and an additional strain peak of 17.5% compared to the expected ones in an ideal model.

	Inner Layer	Mid Layer	Outer Layer	Average	Total
Fiber angles [°]	+60/-60	0/0	-60/+60	-	[60/-60/0] _s
Average thickness [μm]	43.69	34.51	44.17	40.79	122.4
Minimum thickness [μm]	27.34	19.2	25.56	-	95.06
Maximum thickness [μm]	74.69	66.11	71.1	-	164.94
Standard deviation [μm]	7.06	5.01	7.99	6.68	10.51
Percentage of total thickness [%]	35.69	28.19	36.09	33.33	100

Table 3: Statistical analysis of the thickness measurements

The combination of material and manufacturing induced imperfections in the form of overlaps, thickness variations in the spread tow, surface errors and wrapping inaccuracies have drastic influences on the foldability of the structure and need to be considered in the design. We have investigated an approach which aims at minimizing the influence of imperfections. To this purpose we alternate the staggering length (L_s) of the layup to place the overlaps in areas with low curvature. Preferred locations are the internal radius R_1 (5.8mm bending radius) and the parts that are conforming to the outer constraint wall (R_C), which in this case has the radius of 12mm. Results show that the strain peaks in the highly loaded areas can be limited to the standard deviation created by material imperfections, which can be taken into account by adding a safety margin of 10%. According to the numerical results (Figure 6), Layups 2 and 3 (Table 2) are well suited for the packaging scheme, when thicker regions of the layups can be placed in lower strain areas.

6 EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION OF FOLDABILITY

To verify that the design and foldability, we manufactured rings of Layup 2 and 3. The rings were folded into their respective shapes by utilizing a 3D-printed PLA folding jig that enforces the folding radii onto the structure during pinching and twisting. The structure and its folding jig can be seen in Figure 9. The structure is pinched by hand and inserted into the jig (II) following a twisting motion around a pin with radius R_2 with three steel cylinders prescribing R_3 (III). Following the rotation, the structure is constrained in a cylindrical part and the steel cylinders removed (IV). In a last step (V), the jig is removed and the structure equilibrates itself.

Figure 9: Folding the manufactured ultra-thin composite rings into prescribed folding pattern

The folded structures were then casted into clear casting epoxy and examined with regard to shape and possible damages induced during the folding process. Figure 10 shows stitched microscope images with 20x magnification of the two folded layups. Both structure withstood the folding procedure without failure. While Layup 2 shows an almost fully symmetric shape, Layup 3 has slight folding asymmetries induced by the folding process. Nevertheless, Figure 10 also shows the comparison between finite element model and the actual folded structure. It shows, that non-linear finite element simulation is able to predict the deformed shapes showing good agreement between simulation and reality. However, asymmetries from folding lead to deviations between predicted and true shape. In this case, the bottom and top right lobe of Figure 10 show good agreement with simulation, where the top left lobe tip slightly deviates as a consequence of unequal arc length of the three lobes. The slight decrease in bending radii was however not critical due to the introduced safety margins.

Figure 10: Micrograph of fully folded structures with a $[60,-60,0]_s$ layup (left), a $[-30,0,0,+30]$ layup (middle) and the comparison between simulations and experiment of the symmetric layup (right)

To deploy the structure, the cylinders have to be pushed out of their constraint. The stored elastic energy is released in a rapid deployment back to its cylindrical shape. Figure 11 shows such deployment of a structure with Layup 2 in a 2MPa stiff silicone vessel, which was captured with a

high-speed camera (Photron Fast CAM Mini) at 7500FPS. The vessel was 3% smaller than the diameter of the cylindrical shell, simulating a possible deployment and fixation in an aortic tissue.

Figure 11: Deployment of the folded $[60,-60,0]_s$ structure inside an undersized silicone constraint

The deployment takes 34ms and the structure fully retains its cylindrical shape, demonstrating that the introduced folding pattern, the design and manufacturing of the structures are able to produce functional expanding shells outside of the scale of classical composite structures.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a novel design for deployable ultra-thin composite structures. Based on radially expanding cylindrical shells, we show that for a reliable design of ultra-thin structures that require the maximum amount of stiffness while underlying strict packaging constraints, it is crucial to connect folding pattern, structure anisotropy, manufacturing technique and the knowledge about their associated imperfections in a holistic design approach. Although unavoidable manufacturing imperfections are in the micrometer scale, they have a significant effect on strain peaks and hence folding performance. Therefore, accurate predictions of the packaged shapes resulting from the folding pattern are mandatory to place thickness jumps in form of overlaps or ply drops which often are required for the manufacturing of such structures. Ultra-thin composite structures undergo large deformations and behave differently from thick specimen, which makes non-linear experimental analysis of the specific layups a decisive factor for the stiffest layup choice that is packagable into the desired radii.

Result of the novel design are ultra-low thickness structures that are able to show novel functionalities commonly not associated with the stiff material. This includes the utilization of bending radii below 2mm to package a carbon fiber composite structure inside radii of the size of a catheter. Following packaging, the structures remain stiff enough to deploy in a constraint environment fulfilling scale and mechanical requirements of an aortic implant.

Additional investigations should include non-linear fiber behavior for accurate strain predictions in the fiber and matrix, micro cracking and viscoelastic effects during the large deformations, which were not in the scope of this study and are likely to further improve the design. Furthermore, biocompatible polymer systems have to be investigated to enable the design of novel fiber reinforced implants.

8 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the ETH Strategic Focus Area “Advanced Manufacturing “. We thank A. Lamaro and D. Ghedalia for their contribution to the platen tests the measurement of the composite rings.

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